

Fluorescent Detection of Iodide Ions using Coumarin Derivatives: Insights into Electron Transfer Mechanism

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Abstract

Sensitive and reliable detection of iodide ion (I^-) is of considerable importance due to its vital role in environmental, biological, and industrial systems. In the present study, the iodide ion sensing capabilities of three the structurally different coumarin derivatives namely, 6-chloro-4-(4-methoxyphenoxyethyl)-chromen-2-one (S1), 1-(4-methoxyphenoxyethyl)-benzo[f]chromen-3-one (S2), and 6-methoxy-4-(4-methoxyphenoxyethyl)-chromen-2-one (S3) are systematically investigated in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) at room temperature. Steady-state and time-resolved fluorescence spectroscopic techniques are employed to evaluate these interactions. Fluorescence experiments through incremental addition of iodide ions revealed the quenching of coumarin derivatives fluorescence, and analysis was carried out using Stern–Volmer plots to examine the mechanism. The change in Gibbs free energy change (ΔG^0), is estimated to explore the role of photoinduced electron transfer (PET). In addition, the capabilities of investigated coumarin derivatives for rapid and visual detection of iodide ion is examined by solution mode detection method. This study provides a comprehensive assessment of coumarin-based fluorophores as sensing platforms for iodide ion detection.

Keywords:

Iodide ion sensing; Coumarin derivatives; Fluorescence quenching; Photoinduced electron transfer (PET); Stern–Volmer analysis.

1. Introduction

The detection and monitoring of halide ions in environmental and biological systems are crucial for ensuring ecological sustainability and protecting public health [1,2]. Halide ions play diverse roles in natural ecosystems; however, their imbalance arising either from excessive accumulation or deficiency can result in severe environmental degradation and adverse biological effects. Elevated halide concentrations contribute significantly to air, soil, and water pollution, while insufficient availability in natural resources such as drinking water and agricultural soils can disrupt ecological equilibrium and physiological processes in living organisms [3]. The most prevalent halide ions encountered in natural and anthropogenic environments include fluoride (F^-), chloride (Cl^-), bromide (Br^-), and iodide (I^-), originating

from sources such as seawater, mineral deposits, industrial effluents, agricultural runoff, and household products [4,5].

Among these halides, iodide ions merit special attention due to their indispensable role in thyroid hormone synthesis and neurological development in humans and animals [6]. Both iodide ions deficiency and excessive intake are associated with serious health disorders, including goiter, hypothyroidism, hyperthyroidism, and an increased risk of thyroid cancer [7,8]. Consequently, precise monitoring of iodide ions level in environmental and biological samples has become a critical public health concern. Furthermore, the uncontrolled discharge of iodide ions and other halide ions containing industrial wastes poses significant threats to aquatic ecosystems, necessitating the development of sensitive, selective, and reliable detection strategies for iodide and other halide ions [9].

Traditional analytical techniques such as ion chromatography, electrochemical methods, titration, and precipitation-based assays offer accurate halide quantification; however, these approaches often suffer from drawbacks including high operational costs, complex instrumentation, time-consuming procedures, and limited portability [10,11]. These limitations restrict their applicability for rapid, on-site, and real-time monitoring. In contrast, fluorescence-based sensing techniques have emerged as powerful alternatives due to their high sensitivity, operational simplicity, low detection limits, and rapid response times [12,13]. Notably, solution-mode fluorescence sensing has exhibited high efficiency for iodide ions detection across diverse experimental conditions, facilitating convenient visual monitoring [14].

In recent years, organic fluorescent probes have attracted considerable interest for halide ion sensing owing to their structural versatility and tunable photophysical properties. Several representative fluorescent systems have been reported, including polyethyleneimine-templated silver nanoclusters [15], quinolinium derivatives [16], quinine sulfate [17], aminoquinoline-based probes [18], and various coumarin based sensors [19]. Among these, coumarin derivatives stand out as promising candidates due to their rigid conjugated benzopyrone framework, high photostability, and excellent fluorescence quantum yields. Importantly, the tunable intramolecular charge transfer (ICT) characteristics of coumarin scaffolds allow efficient modulation of fluorescence emission in response to external stimuli, and electron transfer processes [20,21].

Motivated by these advantages, the present study explores the iodide ion sensing capabilities of three structurally different coumarin derivatives: 6-chloro-4-(4-methoxyphenoxy)methyl-chromen-2-one (S1), 1-(4-methoxyphenoxy)methyl-benzo[f]chromen-3-one (S2), and 6-methoxy-4-(4-methoxyphenoxy)methyl-chromen-2-one (S3). In these derivatives, the methoxy and phenoxy substituents function as electron-donating groups, while the coumarin carbonyl moiety acts as an electron acceptor, promoting efficient intramolecular charge transfer (ICT). This structurally different electronic configuration of investigated derivatives enhances their sensitivity towards iodide ions detection [22]. In this work, the sensing behavior and underlying interaction mechanisms of the coumarin derivatives were systematically explored using steady-state and time-resolved fluorescence spectroscopic techniques, Stern–Volmer plots and photoinduced electron transfer (PET). The limit of detection (LOD) was determined to evaluate the sensitivity and analytical performance of these probes toward iodide ions. Furthermore, solution-mode fluorescence studies were conducted to examine their practical applicability and visual detection capability. Through these comprehensive investigations, this study aims to elucidate the fundamental aspects of coumarin–iodide interactions and to develop efficient fluorescence-based sensing platform for iodide ions detection.

2. Experimental Section

2.1 Materials

The coumarin derivatives S1, S2, and S3 were synthesized by our research group as reported previously [23] and were employed in the present study without further purification. The molecular structure of the investigated coumarin derivatives are illustrated in Fig 1. Analytical-grade potassium iodide (KI) was procured from S.D. Fine Chemicals Ltd., India, and used as received. Spectroscopic-grade dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) served as the solvent for all spectroscopic measurements.

Fig. 1 Molecular structure of investigated coumarin derivatives.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Preparation of Solutions

The solutions of the coumarin derivatives were prepared in spectroscopic grade DMSO at a concentration of 5×10^{-5} M to minimize self-absorption effects and prevent molecular aggregation. For the interaction and sensing studies, the concentration of iodide ions in DMSO was systematically varied in the range of 0.00 M to 2.55×10^{-3} M.

2.2.2 Spectroscopic Measurements

The UV–Visible absorption spectrum of coumarin derivatives was recorded at room temperature using a LABINDIA UV-3092 spectrophotometer over the wavelength range of 225 – 400 nm. Steady-state fluorescence emission spectrum was collected with an Agilent Cary Eclipse-3000 spectrofluorometer in the spectral window of 350 – 600 nm. The UV–Visible absorption and Steady-state fluorescence measurements of coumarin derivatives were carried out both in the absence and presence of iodide ions.

2.2.3 Fluorescence Lifetime Measurements

Fluorescence lifetime measurements of coumarin derivatives were carried out at room temperature in DMSO using a Horiba DeltaFlex picosecond time-correlated single-photon counting (TCSPC) system, equipped with a high-performance photodiode detector (HPPD) and a Mai Tai pulsed laser as the excitation source. Measurements were performed both in the absence and presence of iodide ions. The resulting fluorescence decay profiles were analyzed by the bi-exponential decay model.

2.2.4 Cyclic Voltammetry Measurements

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) measurements of the coumarin derivatives in DMSO were performed using a CH Instruments CHI708E electrochemical workstation. All experiments

were conducted at room temperature (303 K) in 5 mL voltammetric cell employing a conventional three-electrode configuration, comprising of a glassy carbon working electrode (3 mm diameter), a platinum wire counter electrode, and an Ag/AgCl reference electrode. Prior to each measurement, the glassy carbon electrode was thoroughly polished with a 0.05 μm alumina slurry on a polishing cloth to ensure a clean and reproducible electrode surface. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded at a scan rate of 10 mV s^{-1} .

2.2.5 Solution-Mode Detection of Iodide Ions

For solution-mode detection, 5×10^{-5} M of coumarin derivatives in DMSO was used. For the prepared coumarin solution, 3.64×10^{-4} M and 2.55×10^{-3} M concentration of iodide ions were added. The corresponding changes in fluorescence emission were visually monitored under UV illumination using 8 W, 395 nm UV lamp.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Effect of Iodide Ions on the Absorption Characteristics of Coumarin Derivatives

The UV–Visible absorption spectrum of the investigated coumarin derivatives recorded in the absence and presence of iodide ions is presented in Fig 2. In the absence of iodide ions, the absorption spectrum of S1 and S2 exhibit two well-defined absorption bands. For S1, the bands are centered at 272 nm and 322 nm, while S2 displays absorption maxima at 275 nm and 340 nm. In contrast, the absorption spectrum of S3 shows three prominent absorption peaks, located at 260 nm, 320 nm, and 350 nm.

For all the three coumarin derivatives, the high-energy absorption band observed in the range of 260–275 nm is attributed to the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition associated with the aromatic coumarin framework [24,25]. The lower-energy absorption band appearing in the range of 320–340 nm originates from extended $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions, which arise due to increased conjugation and electronic perturbation induced by the chloro, benzo-fused, and methoxy substituents present in S1, S2, and S3 respectively [26]. Notably, S3 exhibits an additional absorption band at 350 nm, which can be ascribed to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition which arises from the strong push–pull interaction generated by the two methoxy donor groups, which enhances molecular polarization and intramolecular charge transfer in the coumarin framework.

Upon gradual addition of iodide ions, the absorption maxima of the coumarin derivatives remained unchanged, while a progressive decrease in absorbance was observed without the emergence of new bands at longer wavelengths, indicating the involvement of weak, non-covalent interactions [19]. A weak absorption band at 242 nm is attributed to iodide ion absorption. In addition, a new absorption band at 262 nm corresponding to triiodide (I_3^-) showed a gradual increase in absorbance with increasing iodide concentration for all the derivatives [27]. For S3 derivative, a peak at 262 nm is also coinciding with one of its characteristic peaks. These two peaks are matching with absorption peaks of iodide ion and triiodide respectively. The tri-iodide is formed through the reaction $\text{I}_2 + \text{I}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{I}_3^-$ [27]. The lack of new absorption bands indicates that no stable ground-state complex is formed between the coumarin derivatives and iodide ions [28].

Fig. 2 Absorption spectrum of coumarin derivatives in the absence and presence of iodide ions.

3.2 Effect of Iodide Ions on the Fluorescence Characteristics of Coumarin Derivatives

The steady-state fluorescence spectrum of coumarin derivatives S1, S2, and S3 was recorded by exciting S1 at 322 nm, S2 at 340 nm and S3 at 350 nm in the absence and presence of iodide ions. The resulting spectra are presented in Fig 3. In the absence of iodide ions, the fluorescence behavior of the three derivatives reflects distinct excited-state relaxation pathways governed by their molecular structures. Derivative S1 exhibits dual fluorescence bands centered at 408 nm and 495 nm, which are attributed to emissions from the locally excited (LE) state and the intramolecular charge transfer (ICT) state, respectively [29]. The presence of the electron-withdrawing chloro substituent on the coumarin core in S1 enhances excitation localization, favoring LE emission, while the anisyl-methoxy moiety acts as an electron donor, facilitating charge transfer toward the carbonyl acceptor and giving rise to the ICT band [30]. In contrast, S2 and S3 exhibit single fluorescence bands at 443 nm and 416 nm, respectively, due to substitution-induced ICT, where the benzo-fused ring in S2 and the electron-donating methoxy group in S3 enhance donor-acceptor interaction and suppress the locally excited (LE) emission [31].

Fig. 3 Fluorescence spectrum of coumarin derivatives in the absence and presence of iodide ions.

Upon gradual addition of iodide ions, all the three coumarin derivatives show a pronounced and progressive decrease in fluorescence intensity without any observable shift in emission maxima or emergence of new emission bands in the longer wavelength region. This behavior clearly indicates efficient fluorescence quenching of coumarin derivatives by iodide ions while preserving the intrinsic emissive states of the fluorophores. The absence of spectral shifts or new emissive features rules out the formation of exciplexes or excimer formation in the quenching mechanism [32].

To quantitatively evaluate the quenching process, Stern–Volmer (S–V) plots are drawn using Equation (1)

$$\frac{I_0}{I} = 1 + K_{SV}[Q] \quad (1)$$

Here, I_0 and I denote the fluorescence intensity in the absence and presence of iodide ions, respectively, $[Q]$ represents the iodide ion concentration, and K_{SV} is the Stern–Volmer quenching constant. The corresponding plots are shown in Fig 4. For all the three derivatives, a linear relationship between I_0/I versus $[Q]$ was observed with intercept close to unity over the investigated concentration range, confirming the dominance of dynamic quenching pathway [33]. The K_{SV} values, along with the bimolecular quenching rate constants (k_q), calculated using the relation $K_{SV} = k_q\tau_0$, where τ_0 is the fluorescence lifetime of coumarin derivatives in the absence of iodide ions are summarized in Table 1.

Fig 4. Stern–Volmer plots of I_0/I versus $[Q]$

Table 1. Fluorescence quenching parameters of coumarin derivatives with Iodide ions.

Derivatives	$K_{SV} (M^{-1})$	$k_q (M^{-1}s^{-1})$ ($\times 10^{11}$)	$k_d (M^{-1}s^{-1})$ ($\times 10^{11}$)	$K'_{SV} (M^{-1})$	$k'_q (M^{-1}s^{-1})$ ($\times 10^{11}$)
S1	240	2.17	0.84	191	1.54
S2	691	5.45	0.81	666	4.86
S3	332	2.68	0.74	234	2.11

To further validate the nature of the quenching process, time-resolved fluorescence measurements were performed at increasing iodide ion concentrations and are presented in Fig 5. As shown in Fig 5, a systematic shortening of the fluorescence lifetime was observed for all three coumarin derivatives with increasing iodide concentration. The fluorescence decay curves were analyzed using a bi-exponential decay model. The χ^2 values, being close to unity, confirm the good quality of fitting. The reduction in excited-state lifetimes directly supports a dynamic quenching mechanism, consistent with the steady-state Stern–Volmer analysis [34].

Fig. 5 Fluorescence decay profile of coumarin derivatives in the absence and presence of iodide ions.

The quenching behaviour was further evaluated by Stern-Volmer plots τ_0/τ versus iodide ion concentration $[Q]$ (Fig 6), where τ_0 and τ are the fluorescence lifetimes in the absence and presence of iodide ions respectively. The resulting plots exhibit good linearity, and the corresponding Stern–Volmer constants (K'_{SV}) and bimolecular quenching rate constants (k'_q), are summarized in Table 1. Notably, the K'_{SV} and k'_q values obtained from time-resolved lifetime measurements are slightly lower than those derived from steady-state fluorescence quenching for all coumarin derivatives in the presence of iodide ions. This slight discrepancy

indicates that the quenching mechanism is not purely dynamic in nature but likely involves contributions from other mechanisms [33].

Fig. 6 Stern–Volmer plots of τ_0/τ versus $[Q]$

The quenching process can be further rationalized within the framework of diffusion-controlled intermolecular interactions. The diffusion-controlled rate constant (k_d) for bimolecular quenching can be estimated using the Umberger–Lamer equation [35]

$$k_d = 4\pi NRD \text{ in } (\text{M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}) \quad (2)$$

where R is the distance of closest approach, taken as the sum of the molecular radii of the fluorophore (R_F) and the quencher (R_Q), N is Avogadro's number and D is the mutual diffusion coefficient which is calculated by Stokes–Einstein relation [36]. The molecular radius of the coumarin derivatives is calculated using Suppan's method [37]. The calculated molecular radii of the coumarin derivatives S1, S2 and S3 were found to be 4.72 Å, 4.89 Å, and 4.78 Å, respectively. The effective ionic radius of iodide ion is 2.20 Å and is obtained from literature [16]. By substituting the corresponding values into the combined equation, k_d were estimated, and the obtained results are summarized in Table 1. From Table 1, it is observed that the k_q values are higher than the k_d values, indicating that the quenching process is not solely controlled by diffusion [18].

As summarized in Table 1, the K_{SV} follows the trend of $S2 > S3 > S1$. Among these derivatives S2 exhibits the highest Stern–Volmer constant, indicating superior quenching efficiency toward iodide ions compared to S3 and S1. The enhanced sensitivity of S2 could be due to its extended π -conjugation and greater electron delocalization arising from the fused benzene ring, which increases the susceptibility of the excited state toward dynamic quenching by iodide ions. In contrast, S3 and S1 exhibit comparatively reduced charge-transfer efficiency due to the presence of methoxy and chloro substituents, which provide less effective conjugative extension.

3.3 Electrochemical Studies of Coumarin Derivatives

The electrochemical behaviour of the coumarin derivatives (S1–S3) was investigated by cyclic voltammetry in DMSO at room temperature, and the corresponding voltammograms are shown in Fig 7. All the three coumarin derivatives exhibit distinct redox responses within the potential window of -1.0 to $+1.0$ V, confirming the electroactive nature of the coumarin framework [38].

Fig. 7 Cyclic voltammograms of coumarin derivatives.

S1 displays a well-defined cathodic peak at -0.76 V with a peak current of -3.98×10^{-6} A, which is attributed to the reduction of the carbonyl (C=O) acceptor unit of the coumarin core. Similarly, S2 and S3 exhibit cathodic peaks at -0.79 V (-4.07×10^{-6} A) and -0.88 V (-3.72×10^{-6} A), respectively, corresponding to the same reduction process. In contrast, the anodic scans of all derivatives show broad oxidation waves in the positive potential region without well-defined reverse peaks, indicative of quasi-irreversible to irreversible electrochemical behaviour [39]. For PET studies, the reduction potential values for coumarin derivatives are taken as their cathodic peak values.

3.4 Photoinduced Electron Transfer Interaction between Excited Coumarin and Iodide Ions

Photoinduced electron transfer (PET) represents a dominant nonradiative decay pathway responsible for fluorescence quenching in coumarin-based fluorophores [28]. Upon photoexcitation, the coumarin derivatives generate electron-deficient excited states that readily undergo quenching in the presence of strong electron donors. In the presence of iodide ions (I^-), which possess strong electron-donating ability and a pronounced heavy-atom effect, efficient interaction with the excited coumarin derivatives occurs, facilitating PET and resulting in significant fluorescence quenching. The absence of exciplex emission upon iodide ions addition indicates that the charge-transfer state relaxes predominantly through nonradiative deactivation rather than radiative recombination. The thermodynamic feasibility of the PET process was evaluated using the Rehm–Weller equation [40], employing experimentally determined redox potentials from cyclic voltammetry along with singlet excitation energies (E_{00}). The Gibbs free energy changes (ΔG^0) for electron transfer from iodide ions to the excited coumarin derivatives were calculated to be -1.72 eV for S1, -1.46 eV for S2, and -1.55 eV for S3, confirming that the PET process is thermodynamically favourable and spontaneous for all derivatives [41]. The observed trend in ΔG^0 values is consistent with the measured values of Stern-Volmer constants from steady state and time resolved quenching data. The electron-transfer rate constants (k_{ET}) [42], obtained from fluorescence quenching experiments, were

found to be $2.00 \times 10^8 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for S1, $8.00 \times 10^{10} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for S2, and $1.00 \times 10^{10} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for S3, indicating highly efficient excited-state electron-transfer kinetics [42].

3.5 Limit of Detection (LOD)

The sensitivity of the coumarin derivatives towards iodide ions was quantitatively evaluated by determining LOD from the fluorescence data. The LOD values were calculated using the standard relation [44] $\text{LOD} = 3\sigma/K_{\text{SV}}$, where ' σ ' represents the standard deviation of the blank fluorescence signal and K_{SV} is the Stern–Volmer quenching constant. The standard deviation obtained from repeated blank measurements. Using the experimentally determined Stern–Volmer constants, the calculated LOD values are found to be $2.50 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ for S1, $8.68 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ for S2, and $1.81 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ for S3. These values are in good agreement with previously reported literature values [14].

Among the three derivatives, S2 exhibited the lowest detection limit, indicating its superior sensitivity towards iodide ions. This enhanced sensing performance is consistent with its higher Stern–Volmer constant, which reflects stronger interaction between the excited fluorophore and iodide ions. The comparatively lower LOD of S2 further suggests more efficient excited-state quenching, likely facilitated by a stronger intermolecular charge transfer character with iodide ions. In contrast, S1 showed the highest LOD, indicating relatively weaker interaction and lower sensitivity, while S3 displayed intermediate behaviour. The comparative analysis confirms that the sensing performance of these coumarin derivatives is governed by the efficiency of excited-state quenching process.

3.6 Solution Mode Detection of iodide ions

Solution-phase detection of iodide ions was evaluated by the gradual addition of iodide solution with concentrations of $3.64 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ and $2.55 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ to 2 mL aliquots of the coumarin derivative solutions ($5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$) prepared in DMSO. Upon incremental addition of iodide ions, all three coumarin derivatives exhibited a pronounced and progressive decrease in fluorescence intensity. Concomitantly, a distinct change in fluorescence was observed under UV illumination, transitioning from bright blue fluorescence to a nearly non-fluorescent state.

The corresponding visual fluorescence responses were photographed and are presented in Fig 8. These qualitative observations are fully in consistent with the steady-state and time-resolved fluorescence quenching behavior as discussed in Section 3.2. The clear and concentration-dependent naked-eye fluorescence response highlights the practical applicability of the investigated coumarin derivatives as simple and effective fluorescent probes for rapid, on-site detection of iodide ions in solution-based sensing platforms.

Fig. 8 Visual fluorescence response of coumarin derivatives under UV illumination upon gradual addition of iodide ions: left – 0 M, middle – $3.64 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, right – $2.55 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$.

4. Conclusion

The investigated coumarin derivatives exhibited significant fluorescence quenching upon the addition of iodide ions. The linearity in S-V plots from steady state and time resolved methods indicated the predominant contribution of dynamic quenching mechanism. The slight difference between Stern-Volmer constants estimated from steady state and time resolved methods indicates the minor contribution from other quenching mechanisms apart from dynamic quenching mechanism. The negative values of change in Gibb's free energy confirmed the thermodynamic feasibility of the quenching process, supporting the involvement of a photoinduced electron transfer (PET) pathway. Among the studied coumarin derivatives, S2 exhibited the highest sensitivity and the lowest limit of detection, which can be attributed to its extended π -conjugation and stronger electron-accepting characteristics. Solution-phase detection experiments further substantiated these results by exhibiting distinct, concentration-dependent fluorescence changes from bright blue to nearly colourless under UV illumination. Overall, these findings establish structurally different coumarin derivatives as promising and portable fluorescent sensors for rapid and on-site iodide ions detection. This study highlights the potential of coumarin-based platforms for selective iodide ions sensing, with prospective applications in environmental monitoring, chemical analysis, and analytical diagnostics.

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Conflict of Interest:

We the authors of this manuscript declare that there is no conflict of interest concerning this work.

Credit authorship contribution statement

Subhani Khanam Nehal: Investigation, Visualisation, Data curation, Formal Analysis, Writing- Original draft preparation, **Renuka Uppar:** Investigation, Data curation, Formal Analysis, **Mayadevi Kalgi:** Data curation, Formal Analysis, Resources, **Mahanthesh M Basanagouda:** Resources, **Suresh Kumar Hegdal Math:** Data curation, Visualization, Resources, **Thipperudrappa Javuku:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Data availability

Data will be available on request.

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